

Synthesis of CuO nanosheets and its applications towards catalysis and antimicrobial activity

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Abstract : The present study aims a simple chemical synthesis of copper oxide nanosheets (CuO nanosheets) using quinic acid as stabilizing agent at room temperature and studied its catalytic activity in reducing 4-nitrophenol as well as antimicrobial activity towards bacteria. Synthesized CuO nanosheets were characterized by using FTIR, XRD, SEM and TEM. CuO nanosheets showed good catalytic activity for the reduction of 4-nitrophenol, but poor antibacterial activity towards Gram negative and no activity against Gram positive bacteria.

Keywords : Copper oxide nanosheets, 4-nitrophenol reduction, catalyst, quinic acid.

Introduction

Now-a-days, metal oxide nanoparticles have gathered more attention in scientific community due to their excellent properties which covers different aspects of material science and solid state physics. The potential use of the metal oxide nanoparticles in solid state chemistry arises from their outstandingly wide range of properties and the structures¹. They show an attractive electronic and magnetic property. The metal oxide nanoparticles exhibit potential applications in different fields such as semiconductors, biomedical, surface coatings, catalysis, medical and in pharmaceutical products. However, copper oxide nanoparticles (CuO NPs) has gained the most significance among all other metal oxide nanoparticles due to its extensive applications in field emission², gas sensing³, magnetic storage media⁴, drug delivery, field emission devices⁵, solar cell technology⁶ and application in lithium ion batteries⁷.

Several chemical and physical techniques have been developed for the synthesis of CuO NPs such as chemical reduction⁸, microwave irradiation⁹, thermal decomposi-

tion¹⁰, vapor deposition¹¹, electrochemical¹² and quick precipitation¹³. Additionally, the nanoparticles with diverse morphology have been prepared by these methods which include nanodendrits¹⁴, nanorods and nanowires¹⁵, nanospheres¹⁶ and nanoflowers¹⁷.

Further, the benefits in the low cost production of CuO NPs compared to the other metal NPs like gold and silver have made them as the possible alternative material in catalysis applications. Several scientists have examined the catalytic activity of NPs by studying the reduction kinetics of 4-nitrophenol¹⁸⁻²¹. 4-Nitrophenol is a most toxic and hazardous chemical found in polluted water, which normally has been released from the explosive, dye manufacturing industries and other agricultural sources^{22,23}. In addition to this, 4-aminophenol acts as a key intermediate for the production of analgesic and anti-pyretic drugs²⁴. Hence, the development of a simple, low cost, effective method to remove 4-nitrophenols from waste water is of great prominence.

Here, we have reported a simple and low cost method for the synthesis of CuO nanosheets using a natural anti-

oxidant quinic acid as stabilizing agent and sodium borohydride as reducing agent. We also aimed to study the catalytic activity of synthesized CuO nanosheets in the reduction of 4-nitrophenol and their antimicrobial efficiency against *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*).

Results and discussion

The X-ray diffraction pattern (Fig. 1) shows the formation of CuO nanosheets. The characteristic 2θ values obtained at 32.5, 35.56, 38.8, 48.9, 53.43, 58.5, 61.7, 66.7, 68.1, 72.7, 75.2 radians suggest the formation of CuO nanostructures. All the corresponding diffraction patterns reveal the CuO nanostructures, in particular the relevant (110), (111), (111), (202), (020), (202), (113), (310), (220), (221), (222) planes indexing that the material formed comprise of monoclinic structure (JCPDS No. 96-410-5686). The purity of CuO is further confirmed by the absence of characteristic impurity peaks. These results represent the formation of pure CuO phase and the material was free from CuSO_4 and Cu_2O . The calculated average grain size using the Debye-Scherrer formula was found to be 192 nm, which is in good agreement with the TEM results (Fig. 3A, B, C).

Further FTIR analysis was carried out to confirm the capping of quinic acid molecules on CuO nanosheets. Fig. 2 shows the FTIR spectra for the synthesized CuO

nanosheets, where the band at 628 cm^{-1} corresponds to the absorption of Cu-O and the bands at 3425 cm^{-1} and 1400 cm^{-1} are due to O-H vibrations and tertiary alcohol (C-OH) group. These results indicate the capping of quinic acid molecules on the surface of CuO nanosheets, which results in the good dispersibility of CuO nanomaterials in aqueous media (data not shown). However, the presence of quinic acid as capping agents in the reaction medium further acts as growth controlling agent for various faces of CuO nanoparticles through adsorption on these surfaces. In this study, quinic acid selectively interacts with the several crystallographic planes of CuO nanoparticles and greatly reduce the rate of growth along crystalline faces resulting the sheet like nanostructure of $\text{CuO}^{25,26}$ (which is also confirmed by SEM and TEM analysis).

TEM and SEM micrographs of CuO nanostructures synthesized at basic pH are shown in Fig. 3. TEM images show the arrangement of CuO as sheet-like structures. However, the formation of CuO sheets is similar to the production of CuO hierarchical nanostructures and the oriented attachment is reason behind the development of CuO sheets, where smaller nanoparticles joined side by side to form sheets of CuO. The TEM images are similar to the previously reported CuO synthesized at high basic conditions²⁶. However, the formation of sheet like structures of CuO also is confirmed by SEM analysis (Fig. 3D). In addition, the EDAX spectrum (Fig. 4A) of

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of the CuO nanosheets.

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of CuO nanosheets.

Fig. 3. HR-TEM microscopic images of synthesized CuO nanosheets : (A) 100 nm magnification, (B,C) 50 nm magnification and (D) SEM image of CuO nanosheets.

the obtained CuO nanosheets confirms the existence of both the elemental oxygen and copper peaks. Also, it nullifies the presence of other impurities.

The SAED pattern for the ensuring nanoparticles is

shown in Fig. 4B. Selected area diffraction pattern shows various diffraction rings of monoclinic CuO nanosheets.

Catalysis studies :

Fig. 4. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern (A) and EDAX spectrum (B) of CuO nanosheets.

The catalytic activity of the synthesized CuO nanosheets was studied by reducing 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol with the help of chemical reducing agent sodium borohydride (NaBH_4) as a classical reaction. The UV-Visible absorption spectra for the reduction of 4-nitrophenol catalyzed by CuO nanosheets is shown in Fig. 5. The 4-nitrophenol is very stable and can be stored long time in water. A solution of 4-aminophenol in water shows a maximum absorption at 297 nm in UV-Visible spectra.

Fig. 5. UV-Visible spectra of reduction of 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol catalyzed by CuO nanosheets Inset : UV-Visible spectra of reduction of 4-nitrophenol with time.

An aqueous solution containing 4-nitrophenol shows a distinct UV absorption peak maximum at 317 nm, which further shifts to 400 nm after the addition of sodium borohydride indicating the immediate generation of the 4-nitrophenolate ion. After adding CuO nanosheets to the reaction mixture, UV-Visible spectrophotometric absorption readings were taken with respect to time. The peak at 400 nm vanished completely, and the appearance of new peak at 297 nm was generated at 48th second of the reaction time, which corresponds to the absorption of 4-aminophenol (Fig. 5 inset). These results indicate the high efficiency of CuO nanosheets towards the reduction of 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol. Reaction was proceeded by the adsorption of both BH_4^- and 4-nitrophenolate ion on the surface of CuO nanosheets and further the transfer of electron took place from BH_4^- to 4-nitrophenolate ion resulting the formation of 4-aminophenol with decreased activation energy of the reaction^{27,28}. Additionally, we tried to do kinetics for the given 4-nitrophenol reduction reaction but due to the less reaction time it was difficult to obtain the kinetics data.

Antimicrobial activity :

Fig. 6 represents the antibacterial activity of CuO

Fig. 6. Well diffusion assay of CuO nanosheets and CuSO_4 against *E. coli* (A) and *S. aureus* (B) bacterial strains.

nanosheets for *E. coli* (in Panel A) and *S. aureus* (in Panel B). A comparative leachability study with copper sulfate solution in a well diffusion assay was performed and the results show that CuO nanosheets demonstrated no antibacterial activity against Gram positive bacteria (*S. aureus*) even at higher concentrations. Similarly, poor antibacterial activity was observed towards Gram negative bacteria (*E. coli*) at higher concentrations (~4000 ppm). However, the activity of CuSO_4 is less compared to that of CuO nanosheets at 4000 ppm concentration indicating the increase in the antibacterial activity of CuO nanosheets towards *E. coli* compared to bulk copper sul-

fate, which is due to smaller size and hence higher surface area of CuO nanosheets results in the higher interaction with bacterial surface, causing death. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) value of CuO nanosheets for *E. coli* is 3000 ppm.

Experimental

Materials :

Copper(II) sulfate, quinic acid, sodium borohydride, sodium hydroxide, Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA), 4-nitrophenol and all other organic solvents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals, Bangalore.

Preparation of CuO nanosheets :

Preparation of CuO nanosheets were carried out by adding each 20 ml solution of NaOH (0.01 M) and NaBH₄ (0.1 M) into a solution mixture containing 20 ml of CuSO₄ (0.01 M) and 20 ml of (0.02 M) at room temperature (30 °C) under vigorous stirring. Reaction mixture containing metal salt, reducing agent and quinic acid were stirred for about 30 min (Scheme 1). The obtained CuO nanosheets were further purified by successively washing with sufficient amount of double distilled water followed by ethanol and finally dried at 60 °C in hot air oven.

General procedure for the reduction of 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol :

1.9 ml of aqueous 4-nitrophenol (1 mM) solution was mixed with 1 ml of freshly prepared aqueous sodiumborohydride (0.1 M) solution and a deep yellow colored solution appeared. Then, 100 µL of freshly prepared CuO nanosheets (0.05%) catalyst was added to the above solution and UV-Visible absorption kinetics were monitored by varying the concentrations of substrates and catalyst to check the completion of 4-nitrophenol reduction.

Antimicrobial activity :

Antimicrobial activity of synthesized CuO nanosheets and CuSO₄ salt were determined by using Gram positive (*S. aureus*), Gram negative (*E. coli*) bacteria with the help of well diffusion method. Activity was performed by swabbing the bacterial culture onto Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) plates containing approximately 8 mm diameter

wells with the help of a sterile cotton bud. 100 µL of freshly prepared aqueous CuO nanosheets dispersions of different concentrations (3000, 4000 mg mL⁻¹) were loaded into the prepared wells. On the other hand the same amount of CuSO₄ solution (4000 ppm) and a standard Ceftazidime/Clavulanic acid (CAC) antibiotic disk were loaded into other wells to compare the activity of CuO nanosheets and justify the activity of CuO nanosheets (leachable). The plates were incubated at 37 ± 2 °C for overnight and the zone of inhibition was determined.

Characterization :

All the catalytic studies were done by using Jasco V-670 UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer and the spectra were measured against double distilled water as blank. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) study was performed at room temperature by a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with Cu Kα radiation (λ = 1.54 Å) over the range of 2θ of 3°–80° with a scanning rate of 4°/min and with a step size of 0.02°. The instrument was calibrated with lanthanum hexaboride (LaB6) prior to analysis. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) analysis was carried out over the range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹ in the diffuse reflectance mode at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ by JASCO FTIR 4100 instrument and the pellets were made using KBr as reference. SEM images and EDS data were obtained by using a Carl Zeiss SEM instrument attached to EVO MA 15. TEM images were taken by dropping the sonicated CuO nanosheets dispersion on Cu grid (200 meshes Cu) and vacuum dried. Then CuO nanosheets were studied using HR-TEM (JEOL JEM 2100) at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV.

Conclusions

A simple, one step chemical method was developed for the synthesis of water dispersible CuO nanosheets using quinic acid as stabilizing agent. The CuO nanosheets synthesized showed prominent catalytic activity towards the reduction of 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol whereas exhibited poor antimicrobial activity towards Gram negative bacteria and no activity against Gram positive bacteria even at a high concentration of 4000 ppm.

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